

Evaluating the impact of nature-based solutions on the provision of water-related and water-dependant ecosystem services

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ABSTRACT

Water scarcity is a pressing issue in the Mediterranean region, exacerbated by overuse of resources for agriculture and the impacts of climate change. Addressing this challenge requires improved water cycle management and the adoption of Nature-based Solutions (NbS) to enhance infrastructure efficiency and sustainability. With the aim of promoting the implementation and assessment of NbS, we have developed a monitoring framework that integrates the assessment of ecological, socio-economic and cultural aspects under the umbrella of the IUCN Global Standard for NbS. A list of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) was selected following standard methodologies. We have applied the framework to five case studies in the Mediterranean region to evaluate its efficiency to assess NbS tailored to local challenges and contexts. As part of the monitoring framework, we used the IUCN self-assessment tool for the Global Standard for NbS, demonstrating adherence of 50–75 % across all case studies. Common KPIs were identified, streamlining monitoring efforts and providing guidance from the design phase onwards. Our monitoring framework offers a comprehensive approach to evaluating NbS interventions, ensuring alignment with global standards and enhancing resilience in water management. By integrating the IUCN Global Standard, it provides robust guidance for future execution, contributing to sustainable water resource management in the Mediterranean and beyond.

Abbreviations

CS Case Study
IUCN GS IUCN Global Standard
FWC-NbS Full-Water Cycle Nature-based Solutions

1. Introduction

Water management in the Mediterranean is currently facing critical environmental and socioeconomic pressures on water resources, including climate change [1]. Water quality degradation [2] and extreme drought are progressively increasing throughout Europe [3,4]. In particular, in the Mediterranean region, water scarcity is intensifying, negatively affecting the availability, quality, and management of water resources both now and in the future [1,5]. Among the available resources, agricultural water use accounts for more than 70 % of water abstraction in the southern and eastern Mediterranean countries [6].

The rising demand and unsustainable over-exploitation of water resources for agricultural irrigation are depleting aquifers, reducing river flows, and causing ecological degradation [7,8], leading to the loss of aquatic ecosystems and water biodiversity [9–11]. Beyond posing a major threat to water environments, the unsustainable use of water resources risks the long-term resilience of agricultural practices [12]. This situation is exacerbated by the increasing impact of climate change and seasonal variability, affecting freshwater resources in already water-stressed areas and potentially leading to water stress in new locations [13,14]. Addressing this challenge requires improvements managing the water cycle, including water harvesting, storage, and distribution in both natural and artificial water bodies, along with the implementation of wastewater treatment, reuse, and efficient water utilisation approaches [5,6,15].

Nature-based Solutions (NbS) can play a significant role in improving the management of the water cycle [16–18] by leveraging natural processes to address several water-related challenges and by

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improving the efficiency of existing grey solutions [19]. NbS are designed to work with ecosystems rather than against them, offering sustainable ways to enhance water availability, quality, and resilience to climate change and contribute to the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and their targets [20]. Developing a nature-based approach to improving the efficiency of existing natural and greywater infrastructure can lead to a more sustainable and optimised response [21], improve the stability and effectiveness of water management [22] and enhance natural capital and ecosystem services [23]. Despite significant progress, there remains a shortage of quantitative and qualitative data to demonstrate their effectiveness, and additional data is needed to evaluate the performance and advancement of current NbS initiatives in EU-funded projects [24], particularly in terms of their resilience, hydrological efficiency, and cost-benefit comparisons with grey infrastructure solutions [25]. Thus, the development and implementation of comprehensive and internally consistent evaluation frameworks for NbS's performance are crucial for building evidence on environmental impact, and social and economic benefits [26,27]. Furthermore, evaluating the impact performance of NbS is fundamental for measuring effectiveness, informed decision-making [28], resilience [29], accountability [30], scalability and mitigation of unintended consequences [31].

Nevertheless, assessing the impacts and performance of NbS is challenging due to the complexity and diversity of interventions, the interdisciplinary nature of NbS, context-specific performance, limited data availability, uncertainty around long-term impacts, lack of standardization, and the need to balance stakeholders' interests [32]. Although several authors have recently proposed different frameworks and tools to establish robust monitoring and evaluation approaches [21, 33–35], each framework has particular features and its own limitations and social and ecological aspects are not equally addressed. For instance, some of these frameworks focus solely on evaluating the impact of NbS [21,29,36], while others include additional elements in their methodology, such as identifying NbS [32,33] and developing and calculating alternative scenarios [33,34]. Furthermore, some frameworks address all the societal challenges [32,34] while others focus on specific challenges such as water management [21], risk reduction [33] urban resilience and urban water cycle [29], and water quality [36]. Some of the frameworks reviewed are developed for specific scales and areas, such as urban areas [29,32] or rural and mountain areas, although the framework is easily applicable to other scales [33]. One of the main challenges identified by Nika et al. in 2020 is that existing frameworks have focused on micro-scale and individual components, neglecting larger scales [21]. Other frameworks are not developed for a specific scale, allowing for greater flexibility in their application across various spatial contexts [34,36]. In terms of KPIs proposed by the frameworks to assess the impact of NbS, they all consider the different co-benefits provided by NbS, not only the environmental aspects, but also the social and economic aspects. Additionally, some frameworks also favour stakeholder engagement processes as part of their methodology. For example, the framework proposed by Caroppi and colleagues in 2023 proposes involving stakeholders in the definition of the KPIS through questionnaires [33]. In the case of Jegatheesan and colleagues [36], the co-development of the framework is proposed, defining the KPIs with the stakeholders.

The assessment framework proposed in this work tries to integrate three main aspects of NbS impact evaluation: Ecosystem Services, Societal Challenges and Place Context. Previous works already include these elements (such as ecosystem services [37] and societal challenges [32]) which are widely recognized as fundamental and have been reviewed by Nika and colleagues [21]. We have developed a framework that incorporates the IUCN GS for NbS as an overarching guide. Some studies have incorporated the Global Standard self-assessment tool with the aim of improving the sustainability of existing NbS [38,39]. In this case, the application of the IUCN Global Standard helped to identify corrective measures and address development challenges. In other cases,

the application of the standard has enabled the standardisation of the NbS implementation process to achieve more significant benefits [39]. However, these studies do not introduce new frameworks, rather they present use cases of the application of the Standard. The inclusion of the IUCN GS serves as an umbrella that ensures the framework comprehensively addresses the interconnectedness of ecosystem services, societal challenges, and the specific contexts of places. This ensures a (i) holistic approach to NbS evaluation, aligning with global best practices while being adaptable to local conditions and priorities; (ii) consideration and measurement of the positive impacts of localised NbS on the entire water cycle, including upstream and downstream effects and interactions at the watershed level [40]; and (iii) employs user-friendly tools and methods that engage stakeholders to support decision-making and replication of NbS processes.

The IUCN GS, recognized for its straightforward approach and integration of stakeholder input, offers a holistic framework encompassing social, economic, and environmental aspects, alongside biodiversity and climate change considerations [41]. This framework aligns with the global principles identified as essential for robust assessment [32,34]. By adopting the IUCN Standard, this study ensures adherence to internationally recognized guidelines, which enhances the framework's applicability and credibility across diverse regions and contexts [38]. Further, standardization through the IUCN GS improves consistency in data accessibility, decision-making, and stakeholder engagement [34]. It also facilitates broader adoption and comparability, fostering learning and continuous improvement [42,43].

This study presents a monitoring framework designed to be replicable in Mediterranean regions facing similar water management challenges. To the best of our knowledge, it is the first attempt to integrate socioeconomic, cultural, and ecological factors through the application of the IUCN GS for NbS, combined with key performance indicators (KPIs) tailored to ecosystem services, in line with the European Commission's guidelines for evaluating NbS [42]. By addressing the entire water cycle and considering context-specific challenges, the framework aims to facilitate more informed decision-making, policy development, and project implementation. The NATMed project (<https://natmed-project.eu/>) seeks to improve water management in the Mediterranean by implementing innovative NbS combined with applied technologies that span all phases of the water cycle (referred to as Full Water Cycle NbS, or FWC–NbS). Our work demonstrates how the proposed framework can be applied within the NATMed project and its five Case Studies, providing a practical approach for managing water resources in the region.

2. The framework

2.1. Framework structure

The framework is structured around three interconnected core pillars that facilitate a comprehensive evaluation of NbS impacts (see Fig. 1):

- a) A common set of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) to assess the environmental, social, and economic benefits, as well as the associated co-benefits, of enhanced water resource management.
- b) A unified monitoring methodology designed to compare and assess the implementation of these KPIs across different interventions.
- c) Continuous monitoring of these KPIs in NbS implementation areas, including, where applicable, an evaluation of upstream and downstream effects to capture impacts across the entire water cycle.

The KPIs are further linked to three essential components that provide a broader context for the framework's application. First, the KPIs are connected to water-related and water-dependent ecosystem services (ES) [44]. Second, the framework aligns the KPIs with key societal challenges, such as water security, food security, human health, disaster risk reduction, climate change adaptation and mitigation,

Fig. 1. Conceptual scheme for the monitoring framework for NbS impact assessment. The framework is structured around three interconnected core pillars: common KPIS, a unified monitoring methodology and water cycle monitoring including upstream and downstream effects. The KPIS are linked to three components under the umbrella of the IUCN GS: Ecosystem Services, Societal Challenges, and Local Context.

socio-economic development, and biodiversity conservation [45]. Finally, the framework emphasizes the importance of selecting the most relevant KPIS for each case study, taking into account the specific context, challenges, and anticipated interventions. Finally, the IUCN Global Standard for NbS serves as an additional layer of the framework under which the other elements are integrated, providing a structured and internationally recognized set of criteria to further assess and scale the social, economic, and environmental impacts of NbS interventions. This standard ensures that the framework aligns with global best practices, fostering consistency and credibility in the evaluation process across different contexts and regions [41,46].

2.2. Monitoring and selection of KPIS

As with many other frameworks, the initial step in monitoring the impacts of NbS is to choose a comprehensive set of KPIS. The selection of KPIS must be tailored to address the specific characteristics of each case in order to accurately assess the environmental, social, and economic impacts of NbS. The KPIS outlined here have been drawn from the 'Evaluating the Impact of Nature-Based Solutions: A Handbook for Practitioners' though many other valuable resources are also available for consideration [42].

The selected KPIS are grouped according to two classifications. First, KPIS are divided into water-related and water-dependent ES, following the United Nations World Water Development Report [47]. Second, the KPIS are further divided into four categories, following the Millennium Ecosystem Assessment classification: Provisioning, regulating, cultural and supporting KPIS [48,49]. Thus, we achieve a classification of KPIS that considers a twofold perspective at the same time: water management and ES classification related to water. The KPIS are also linked to the societal challenges addressed by NbS, established by the International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN) - water security, food security, human health, disaster risk reduction, climate change adaptation and mitigation, socioeconomic development, ecosystem degradation and biodiversity loss [46]. Table 1 shows the ES classification, and the link between ES and the challenges addressed by the intervention area.

The set of KPIS is shared across all case studies, and while not every KPIS is monitored in each case, we have identified key indicators that are common to two or more CS. To facilitate the comparability of KPIS across the case studies, we established a unified monitoring methodology. This involves monitoring KPIS upstream, within, and downstream of the intervention area, when possible. Additionally, we have applied standardized monitoring methods based on the expertise of each case study team, allowing for better consistency in data collection. This approach also helps to identify common monitoring frequencies across

the different sites. Supplementary Table 2 shows the full list of KPIS and their link with societal challenges and ES.

2.3. Integration of the IUCN global standard for nature-based solutions

The framework integrates the eight criteria of the IUCN GS for NbS. The aim of these criteria is to create a common framework for the design and evaluation of NbS. The eight criteria refer to (1) NbS effectively address societal challenges; (2) Design of NbS is informed by scale; (3) NbS result in a net gain to biodiversity and ecosystem integrity; (4) NbS are economically viable; (5) NbS are based on inclusive, transparent and empowering governance processes; (6) NbS equitably balance trade-offs between the achievement of their primary goal(s) and the continued provision of multiple benefits; (7) NbS are managed adaptively, based on evidence; (8) NbS are sustainable and mainstreamed within an appropriate jurisdictional context [41]. More detailed information on the criteria is included in the Supplementary Table 1. The assessment, self-conducted by each of the case studies and then reviewed, provides an overall rating of how well the design of the proposed NbS adheres to the Standard, for which a traffic light system per indicator is used, going from "Strong adherence" (dark green) to "Insufficient" (red). If one of the interventions scores an "Insufficient" rating on any Criterion (the average value of the indicators within it), it would not be in adherence with the GS and therefore could not be qualified as an NbS according with the IUCN [12].

To incorporate and evaluate the eight criteria outlined by the IUCN GS, our monitoring framework establishes clear connections between the KPIS, ecosystem services, and these criteria. Criterion 1's adherence is reflected in all KPIS, as they all relate directly or indirectly to one of the societal challenges set by the IUCN; criterion 2 is covered by those indicators that address the interactions that occur across different social and ecological scales within the landscape, as those belonging to ES such as Water purification and waste treatment/quality, Drought protection, Regulating services, Intervention in protected areas or Cultural ES; criterion 3 is covered by KPIS related to Habitat for species or Soil healthy; criterion 4 is addressed by KPIS related to Tourism, Sustainable economic development and Creation of new jobs; criterion 5 is covered by indicators related to Social justice, Education or Degree of satisfaction; all of the water-related ecosystem services contribute to the assessment of criterion 6, as well as Habitat for Species, Soil healthy, Intervention in protected areas or economic related indicators; criterion 7 is addressed by all the KPIS indirectly, as they must be part of a comprehensive monitoring and evaluation plan that measures impact throughout the NbS lifecycle and allows for adaptive management based on evidence; lastly, criterion 8 is covered by KPIS related to legal context, Replication,

Table 1
Identification of Ecosystem Services (ES). ES are classified according to water management aspects. The “Challenge” column provides additional information about the specific challenge each ES addresses.

Challenge	Ecosystem Service	
	Water-related ES	
Water Security	Provisioning services	Freshwater supply for drinking/irrigation Reused water supply for irrigation Water quantity
Water Security	Regulating services	Water regulation Erosion regulation Water purification and waste treatment / water quality
Disaster risk reduction		Natural hazard regulation - Drought protection Natural hazard regulation - Flood protection Natural hazard regulation - coastal protection
Climate Change Challenge		Climate regulation/moisture recycling
Food Security	Water-dependent ES	
Socioeconomic development	Provisioning services	Food and fibre Energy Genetic resources Biochemicals, natural medicines, pharmaceuticals Raw material
Human health	Regulating services	Air quality regulation Climate regulation
Climate Change		Pollination
Biodiversity		Pest and disease regulation
Socioeconomic development		Legal Context
Biodiversity	Supporting services	Habitat for species
Food Security		Soil Healthy
Food security		Nutrient cycling
Food security		Primary production
Biodiversity		Interventions in protected areas
Socioeconomic development		Replication
Socioeconomic development	Cultural services	Spiritual, religious and totemic values Recreation and health Tourism Education Social Justice Sustainable economic development Creation of new jobs Sustainable Development Goals Degree of Satisfaction Aesthetic appreciation and inspiration for culture, art and design

Education and Sustainable Development Goals. The full list of KPIs in relation to the criteria is included in Supplementary Table 2.

2.4. Application of the framework to real case studies

2.4.1. The case studies: geographical and environmental context

The five case studies selected for this study illustrate the great geographical, economic and social diversity of the Mediterranean region (Fig. 2A). These five case studies have been selected to cover the optimization of different water infrastructures and various challenges related to water management. In Case Study 1 (Carrión de los Céspedes, Spain), the focus is on improving wastewater recovery for irrigation and reduce evaporation rates of stored water. Case Study 2 (Lake Chimaditida, Greece) is part of a natural wetland complex and focuses on strengthening the capability of natural wetlands to store and treat water through natural management and pollution discharge control. The aim of case Study 3 (Arborea, Italy) is to improve groundwater storage and quality by upgrading existing nature-based practices to mitigate groundwater nitrate contamination. In order to improve the water quantity and quality of groundwater, Case Study 4 (Bozcaada, Türkiye)

Fig. 2. Case studies in the Mediterranean region. A. Global view of the five case studies within the context of the Mediterranean Region. B. Main water reservoir, Carrión de los Céspedes (Seville, Spain). C. Chimaditida lake, Greece. D. FIA system, Arborea, Italy. E. Bozcaada, Türkiye. F. Oued Righ canal, Algeria.

looks at natural infiltration, reduction of surface runoff and improvement of agriculture practices and distribution systems efficiency. In case study 5 (Oued Righ, Algeria), the water quality of the Oued Righ canal will be improved by reducing the discharge of wastewater and agriculture run-offs. All case studies are located in areas categorised as Csa (hot summer Mediterranean) under the Köppen-Geiger climate classification [50], except for the Case Study in Algeria, which falls under a BWh climate area (hot-arid desert). Table 2 shows a summary of the case studies and the challenges encountered and addressed in each region.

2.4.2. Implementation of NbS in the case studies

To implement effective and strategic solutions, sustainable, with maximum environmental and social impact, the designs of the NbS developed in each Case Study consider the challenges and context of the area.

In CS1 (Fig. 2B), to address local challenges and improve the recovery of wastewater for irrigation purposes, we are evaluating and optimising the performance of seven types of constructed wetlands (CWs). The treated water from the CWs will be stored in tanks that will be equipped with floating gardens specifically designed to reduce the evaporation rate in the tanks. One of the tanks will be additionally equipped with an ultrasounds system to reduce the proliferation of microalgae and *Escherichia coli* and improve the water quality. In a final step, we will analyse the effects of the treated water on agricultural soils.

In CS2 (Fig. 2C), two NbS and one technology will be implemented. We are developing a livestock management system in the area to manage the conservation and restoration of the existing lake, and more specifically to control reed beds. Riparian buffers are also being developed on the shores of the lake to improve water quality by reducing pollution from agricultural activities and pesticide run-off. In addition, water distribution systems are being improved by initiating monitoring and developing an irrigation plan that will help reduce water consumption in the region and enhance the lake’s water quantity.

Table 2

Overview of the five case studies selected for the study. Each column highlights their geographical coordinates, location descriptions, and the primary environmental issues they face.

CASE STUDY	COORDINATES	LOCATION DESCRIPTION	MAIN CHALLENGES
CARRIÓN DE LOS CÉSPEDES, SPAIN	37°21'27" N, 6°19'55" W	Experimental site for wastewater treatment and water management; faces drought, water scarcity, and pollution issues.	Drought, water scarcity, pollution, climate change.
CHIMADITIDA LAKE, GREECE	40°36'21.164" N, 21°33'12.780" E	Part of a lake complex; rich biodiversity; faces seasonal drought, groundwater depletion, and eutrophication.	Seasonal drought, groundwater depletion, eutrophication, reed encroachment.
ARBOREA, ITALY	39°43'04" N, 8°33'29" E	Agricultural district	Nitrate Vulnerable Zone. challenges with aquifer contamination and soil fertility management.
BOZCAADA, TÜRKIYE	39°47'15.0" N, 26°03'40.6" E	Small Aegean island; reliant on mainland water supply; faces tourism-related water strain, droughts, and salinity intrusion.	Tourism-driven water demand, droughts, salinity intrusion, erosion.
OUED RIGH, ALGERIA	32°52'00.00" N, 5°59'00.00" E	150 km canal system; supports agriculture and wetlands; faces drought, water scarcity, pollution, and biodiversity loss.	Drought, water scarcity, stagnant water, pollution, biodiversity loss.

In CS3 (Fig. 2D) the Forested Infiltration Area (FIA) system, an already existing NbS, will be updated. The aim is to improve groundwater quality and storage through cost-effective and more efficient technical solutions.

Five NbS and two technologies are used in CS4 (Figure 2E). As part of the Managed Aquifer Recharge (MAR) techniques, in CS4 we are developing NbS for natural infiltration in a declining sub-catchment that is particularly prone to surface runoff risks, with the aim of infiltrating additional water into aquifers. It is also monitoring and installing ten recharge wells to replenish aquifers with freshwater to prevent seawater intrusion into coastal aquifers. Additionally, new groundwater storage systems such as underground dams are being developed to supplement existing aquifers and to store and reuse the water flowing in the riverbeds. We are also developing conservation agriculture practices in a fig (*Ficus carica*) plantation to promote soil health, minimize environmental impacts, and conserve and make the best use of water resources. Further, we will develop climate-resilient agricultural practices to adapt the Paulownia tree cultivation area to changing climatic conditions and to minimize risks associated with extreme weather events such as droughts, floods, storms, and shifting temperature patterns. To facilitate decision-making, Bozcaada's water distribution system is also analyzed by a Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition (SCADA) system to collect information on water consumption and losses from the pipe system. In order to use less water for irrigation, an intelligent irrigation system based on soil moisture monitoring is also being developed on the island.

Two NbS are implemented in CS5 (Fig. 2F): on one hand, a CW pilot

system will be implemented to improve the quality of water discharged into the Oued Righ canal, increase the functionality of the existing wastewater treatment plant and reduce maintenance costs. On the other, we will also establish riparian buffers with macrophyte species on the banks of the canal to act as a natural purification system and protect against agricultural runoff and erosion.

Table 3 summarizes the NbS and other technologies that are implemented or improved in the Case Studies, the main challenges they address (water quantity or quality), and the main ES they provide.

2.4.3. KPI selection and monitoring in the case studies

From the common set of KPIs (listed in Supplementary Table 2), a panel of technical experts selected the most relevant indicators tailored to the specific NbS being implemented, as well as the local context of each Case Study region. These KPIs are also aligned with the eight criteria of the IUCN Global Standard (Supplementary Table 2). Each KPI has an associated standard methodology for measurement and a defined monitoring frequency, ensuring consistency and accuracy in data collection across the Case Studies. In addition, ecosystem services (ES) were identified for each Case Study (Supplementary Table 4). Of the 36 ES listed in Table 3, 25 are being evaluated across the Case Studies. The selection of final ecosystem services is also based on the specific regional context and the type of NbS to be implemented. In particular, Case Study 1 includes 19 ES, Case Study 2 includes 17, Case Study 3 includes 9, Case Study 4 includes 22, and Case Study 5 includes 10 ES (Supplementary Table 4).

2.4.4. Assessment based on the IUCN GS for NbS

During the design phase, we conducted an initial assessment against the eight criteria of the IUCN GS for NbS with the aim of aligning with its guidance and enhancing robustness for future execution. The baseline data for the selected KPIs, collected as part of the monitoring framework, facilitated the evaluation of the criteria outlined in the IUCN GS.

We used the IUCN self-assessment tool for the Global Standard for NbS for each of NATMed's case studies. Fig. 3 illustrates the adherence of each case study to the eight criteria of the Standard. Supplementary Table 3 provides all global score percentages indicating adherence to the eight criteria of the standard for each case study.

The results of each Case Study show that the total percentages of the initial NbS analysis of all Case Studies have adequate adherence to the IUCN GS (50–75 %). CS4 (Türkiye) presents the highest total adherence percentage (66 %) to the IUCN GS and it and adheres to all criteria adequately, exceeding 50 %. Criteria 3 and 8 stand out with a with strong adherence (>75 %). CS1 (Spain) also presents a similar adherence to the standard (65 %). Criteria 6, 7 and 8 stand out with a strong adherence and criteria 2 and 4 have a lower adherence. CS2 (Greece) follows with a similar adherence as well (65 %). It adheres to all criteria adequately, excepting criteria 4 that has a strong adherence (83 %).

The Case Study with the lowest adherence to the standard is CS3 (Italy) with a 52 %. It adheres strongly to criterion 7, adequately to criteria 1, 5, 6 and 8, partially to criteria 2 and 3 and inadequately to criterion 4. CS5 (Algeria) also has a lower adherence to the standard (54 %). It presents an adequate adherence for criteria 1, 2, 3, 5, 7 and partial adherence for criteria 4, 6 and 8.

The individual criterion results demonstrate that each Case Study best adheres to different criteria according to its local context and reality. On average, all criteria have an adequate adherence (between 50 and 75 %), excepting criterion 4 with a partial average adherence of 45 %. The criterion with the best adherence is number 7, with 71 %. Additionally, our results show that certain CS perform surprisingly well in some cases. For example, CS2 adheres better than other CS to criterion 4. Similarly, CS2 and CS4 show a stronger adherence to criterion 7 and criterion 3, respectively, than the other CS.

Table 3

NbS and technologies developed in NATMed Case Studies (CS). Solution: intervention type, can be Nature-based Solutions or other technologies. (MAR: Managed Aquifer Recharge; FIA: Forested Infiltration Area) Challenge: Specific challenge the solutions are intended to address. ES: Ecosystem Services associated to each challenge and solution; CS: Case Study Colored blocks indicate the Case Studies where the solutions will be implemented. CS1: Carrión de los Céspedes, Spain; CS2: Chimaditida Lake, Greece; CS3: Arborea, Italy; CS4: Izmir, Türkiye; CS5: Oued Righ, Algeria.

Solution	Challenge	ES	CS				
Nature-based Solutions							
CW	Water Quality	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reused water supply • Water purification • Habitat species 	1	2	3	4	5
Floating Gardens	Water Quantity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Water quantity • Habitat for species 	1	2	3	4	5
Livestock management	Water Quantity & Quality	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Freshwater supply • Habitat for species 	1	2	3	4	5
MAR: FIA system	Water Quality	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Water regulation • Water purification 	1	2	3	4	5
MAR: Natural Infiltration	Water Quantity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Water quantity • Erosion control 	1	2	3	4	5
MAR: Recharge Wells	Water Quality	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Freshwater supply • Water purification 	1	2	3	4	5
MAR: Groundwater storage	Water Quantity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Water quality • Drought protection 	1	2	3	4	5
Riparian Buffers	Water Quality	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Water regulation • Water purification 	1	2	3	4	5
Conservation Agriculture	Water Quantity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Water regulation • Soil health 	1	2	3	4	5
Climate Resilient Agriculture	Water Quantity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Water regulation • Soil health 	1	2	3	4	5
Other technologies							
Distribution system: Irrigation Plan	Water Quantity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Freshwater supply • Water Quantity 	1	2	3	4	5
Distribution system: Monitoring	Water Quantity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Freshwater supply • Drought protection 	1	2	3	4	5
Ultrasounds	Water Quality	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Water purification • Water quality 	1	2	3	4	5

3. Discussion

Despite numerous initiatives aimed at addressing the lack of a robust and impartial assessment of current NbS measures in water management, there remains a need for a simple and standardized methodology that is easy to implement. Some of the existing frameworks are considerably difficult to implement by non-experts. This lack of expertise is a well-known barrier in NbS implementation, and contributes to the lack of available data [25,33,34]. To address these challenges, we aimed to develop a framework that allows stakeholders to collect qualitative and quantitative data to measure the impacts of the NbS, and considers crucial aspects of NbS evaluation such as local conditions, ecosystem

services and societal challenges. To validate this framework, we are applying it across different Case Studies (CS) within the NATMed project, allowing us to assess its effectiveness in real-world contexts.

In NATMed, we have five Case Studies where different NbS have already been implemented or are planned for implementation. These NbS were or have been proposed taking into account the local context and the challenges of the area. For example, CS1 is located in Seville, Spain, where one of the main challenges is related to water scarcity, not only for consumption but also for agricultural purposes. This scarcity is further worsened by the climate of the area, which is characterized by very dry summer seasons, and little rainfall in the wet seasons. Thus, one of the main problems that we needed to address in this CS is the

NbS Self-assessment Overview

Percentage of adherence to the Standard of the five Case Studies

Fig. 3. NbS self-assessment overview. Result from the application of IUCN self-assessment tool for the GS for NbS on each of the NATMed’s Case Study. Each section refers to the eight criteria of the IUCN GS. Dark blue colour refers to CS1 (Spain); Light green refers to CS2 (Greece); Dark purple colour refers to CS3 (Italy); Yellow colour refers to CS4 (Türkiye); Blue green colour refers to CS5 (Algeria).

evaporation rates of water stored in irrigation reservoirs. Consequently, the CS is assessing the impact of constructed wetlands on water quality, and the impact of floating gardens on water quantity (i.e., on decreasing evaporation rates in irrigation tanks). Although water scarcity and water quality are challenges common to all CS, the context of each area influences how these challenges can be addressed. Measuring the impact of all the implemented or existing NbS is subsequently challenging, and developing standard methodologies becomes particularly crucial when striving to derive meaningful conclusions capable of supporting policy guidelines and recommendations for best practices. To facilitate this, we selected a common set of KPIs that cover environmental, socio-cultural and economic benefits. These KPIs are further tailored to the implemented solutions, and are monitored and measured following standard methods (when possible). The KPIs are continuously monitored to

gather robust and meaningful data, and to facilitate the comparison among CS and similar NbS. This enables the identification of common KPIs across multiple case studies, allowing the data collected during the monitoring of NbS to be more comparable. This further facilitates the evaluation at a global scale, and allows relevant stakeholders to find common best practices that can be replicated in other areas. The standardization of the evaluation is further refined by integrating the IUCN GS for NbS. Although the IUCN GS has been extensively used to evaluate the impacts of NbS implementations (see for example [38,39,51], to our knowledge it still has not been integrated in a framework that encompasses other aspects of NbS evaluation and assessment.

Applying the standard already at the design phase can serve as guidance, offering a path to address aspects such as societal challenges, scale, biodiversity, finance, governance, participation, trade-offs,

monitoring, evaluation, learning, and replicability, thereby informing the selection of KPIs, and allowing for the assessment and monitoring of each criterion through measurable data. Knowing the status of each criterion in the initial and final stages of the monitoring and evaluation period provides insights into specific aspects that require improvement through its eight Criteria. For the purpose of evaluating the level of adherence to the standard, the IUCN has developed a tool (see Section 2.3). The assessment, self-conducted by each of the case studies and then reviewed, has provided an overall rating of how well the design of the proposed NbS adheres to the Standard (Fig. 3). Using the IUCN tool, we were able to set a primary score and identify which aspects of the NbS designs need to be improved (Fig. 3). However, there are some caveats to this method. Despite being an excellent working tool, applying it to pilot NbS projects can be challenging, because it is designed to assess and guide large-scale projects. Small-scale and demonstrative interventions, like some of the interventions planned in NATMed, may have difficulties in effectively meeting some requirements of the Standard, establishing a ceiling beyond which the actual project will no longer be able to adhere to it, unless a scaling-up phase is foreseen. Our framework addresses these caveats partially by, as mentioned previously, including KPIs that are specifically tailored to the needs and context of each Case Study. This allows us to monitor the progress and impacts of the NbS implementation on a case-by-case basis, giving local stakeholders information that can be used at the regional and local level to replicate or scale up the implementations of each pilot. The IUCN Standard has been reported to contribute to being effective at targeting solutions, is straightforward and incorporates stakeholder input [38] and offers a holistic framework that incorporates socio-cultural socio-economic aspects and biodiversity, ecosystems and climate change in relation with societal challenges, which was previously identified as an essential characteristic of holistic frameworks [32,34]. By aligning the monitoring framework with the IUCN Global Standard, we ensure that the proposed approach is consistent with internationally recognised guidelines and principles [38]. Further, the standardisation derived from the application of the standard enhances the credibility and applicability of the framework across different contexts and regions which is in line with our results, facilitating broader adoption and comparability of results [51], ensuring best practices, fostering learning and improvements and adding global credibility [42,43].

On the other hand, existing frameworks have certain limitations, such as the lack of holistic integration and multidimensional approaches to all co-benefits of the NbS. Although there is a variety of indicators developed among the different studies [21], not all aspects of water management are covered, with a minority addressing the improvement of the natural environment. In addition to these limitations, aligning NbS with broader regional and local water management plans presents another significant challenge. For instance, Young et al. (2019) highlighted that upstream interventions often fail to consider downstream regions [52]. Therefore, systemic management and a comprehensive connection of the proposed solutions to a broader scale are necessary [21]. The lack of stakeholder awareness can also be a limitation in existing frameworks. It is necessary to improve stakeholders' perceptions in order to optimise their participation in the definition of KPIs. According to Caroppi and colleagues [33], a higher level of understanding and commitment from stakeholders could significantly improve the results of their involvement in the process.

Although our framework shares many similarities with existing frameworks, its key strength lies in its flexibility and adaptability to different contexts, making it suitable for application across a wide range of geographical regions and water management challenges. This flexibility is achieved by tailoring the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) to address the specific socio-economic, environmental, and cultural factors of each case study, while maintaining a standardized methodology for data collection and impact assessment. Further, the framework is designed so it can be easily scaled and replicated. Once validated in the NATMed project case studies, the proposed framework can be adapted

for use in regions facing similar water management challenges, such as water scarcity, pollution, and biodiversity loss and other pressures derived from climate change. Its modular design allows stakeholders to adjust the set of KPIs according to local conditions while preserving the integrity of the monitoring process. For instance, regions with arid climates can prioritize indicators related to water conservation, while areas facing flooding or eutrophication can focus on water quality and ecological restoration. Moreover, the framework's standardized approach ensures that data collected from different regions remains comparable, facilitating cross-regional analyses and helping to identify best practices that can be applied globally. This comparability is essential for scaling up successful NbS interventions, enabling policy-makers and practitioners to replicate proven solutions in diverse settings. The integration of the IUCN Global Standard further strengthens the framework's replicability, offering a globally recognized set of criteria that guides the design and implementation of NbS, ensuring consistency and credibility across projects. By offering a structured yet flexible framework, we provide a tool that not only supports localized NbS interventions but also creates opportunities for scaling successful solutions to larger regions, or even nationally and internationally. As the framework is applied to more case studies and regions, it has the potential to build a body of evidence that can inform water management policies, strengthen stakeholder engagement, and support the long-term sustainability of natural resources.

4. Conclusions

In this study, we developed and implemented a comprehensive monitoring framework for evaluating the impacts of Nature-based Solutions (NbS) on water management in the Mediterranean region. By integrating the IUCN Global Standard with a tailored set of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), we ensured a holistic approach that accounts for environmental, social, and economic benefits across diverse geographical and socio-cultural contexts. The application of this framework in five case studies demonstrated its flexibility and adaptability, allowing it to address local challenges while maintaining consistency through standardized methodologies. The results from the case studies, especially the adherence to the IUCN Global Standard, indicate that the framework provides a robust tool for NbS evaluation, supporting decision-making and policy development. Furthermore, its scalability and potential for replication across different regions with similar water management challenges make it a valuable contribution to sustainable water resource management. Future work should focus on refining the framework, improving stakeholder engagement, and expanding its application to further assess the long-term impacts of NbS on global water systems.

Impacts

- **Environmental Impacts:** Nature-based Solutions (NbS) contribute to restoring ecosystems and Ecosystem Services provision. NbS implementation address water management challenges, by improving water quality and quantity among other environmental benefits. The proposed monitoring framework facilitates the measurement of NbS contributions to biodiversity, climate change, disaster risk, water and food security through targeted KPIs.
- **Economic Impacts:** A successful implementation of NbS will be cost-effective in the long term and promote sustainable economic development. The proposed monitoring framework facilitates the measurement of NbS contributions to economic development, the emergence of new economic activities, and the generation of green jobs through targeted economic KPIs.
- **Social impacts:** Social aspects are intrinsically embedded in NbS implementation, from social acceptance to improving social cohesion. The proposed monitoring framework facilitates the

measurement of NbS contributions to social justice, satisfaction, perception and education through targeted social KPIs.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Raquel Marijuan: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Bárbara Díez:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Sara Peláez-Sánchez:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Claudia Sánchez:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Jesús Iglesias:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Başar Şirin:** Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation. **Alper Baba:** Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation. **Orhan Gündüz:** Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation. **Raúl Sánchez:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Supplementary materials

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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